

Foundation Model Challenge for Brain MRI 2025: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Foundation Model Challenge for Brain MRI 2025

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

FOMO

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Evidence from general computer vision suggests that large-scale self-supervised pre-training presents vast yet underutilised possibilities in brain MRI analysis. Yet, the current method of choice for deep-learning based analysis of brain MRI is still a fully-supervised paradigm. Due to a highly effective data augmentation pipeline, the fully-supervised approach can be effective even with limited labeled data. However out-of-domain robustness remains challenging, effectively limiting the models from broad clinical deployment. The recent paradigm of training foundation models, by using self-supervised pre-training on large-scale datasets, provides an avenue to remedy this, promising models which can be few-shot adapted to novel tasks, while remaining robust to out-of-domain data.

To spearhead the development of large self-supervised foundation models in the brain MRI domain, we propose FOMO, the first challenge at MICCAI aiming to investigate foundation models for brain MRI. This challenge is designed to drastically reduce the barrier for the MICCAI community to train foundation models. Further, this challenge seeks to investigate the few-shot generalisation properties of foundation models in the context of real-world brain MRI data by evaluating models on three large clinical, multi-vendor, and multi-center datasets. Since models are evaluated on multiple downstream tasks, this challenge seeks to investigate the effects of different pre-training paradigms and configurations on downstream performance and ultimately both identify the most promising methodologies and quantify the benefits of self-supervised pre-training.

In this challenge, participants will have access to the largest brain imaging dataset ever released, assembled from public sources, comprising of 51,779 MRI scans (from 11,161 cases) of which approximately a third are of clinical quality. The pre-training dataset will not contain any segmentation maps or disease diagnosis information which can be used for supervision. Participants will first pre-train a model on this dataset, before fine-tuning models on three few-shot supervised tasks consisting of clinical MRIs spanning image-level infarct detection, meningioma segmentation and brain age estimation. Evaluation consists of large, diverse, multi-vendor, multi-center datasets

consisting of 1200, 600 and 2000 MRI scans (400, 200 and 1000 subjects) respectively. 20% of the data will be made available during a pre-evaluation phase, which allows participants to gauge the performance of their models before final submission.

This challenge is jointly organised by researchers from Pioneer Centre for AI, University of Copenhagen, Massachusetts General Hospital & Harvard Medical School and Bispebjerg & Frederiksberg Hospital, Copenhagen, Copenhagen Research Centre for Biological and Precision Psychiatry & Gentofte Hospital and the Copenhagen-based startup Cerebriu.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Foundation models, self-supervised learning, out-of-domain generalisation, few-shot learning, brain MRI, clinical data

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

This challenge is the first foundation model challenge at MICCAI for brain MRI. The focus on a 3D modality such as MRI and the evaluation of pre-training methods with respect to few-shot generalization to clinical data, we believe is both novel and highly relevant for the continuous development of the field.

Further, the open track of the challenge, where any private data can be included in the (pre-) training, serves as a demonstration of what the community is able to achieve without artificial limitations. This enables researchers around the world to showcase the ability of their foundation models, and provides a window into the future of what can be achieved with larger pre-training datasets.

Lastly, the publicly provided pre-training dataset is the first of its kind, both lowering the barrier of entry for researchers to investigate large-scale self-supervised pre-training methods for brain MRI applications, and providing a level playing field to compare various approaches.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

The primary aim of this challenge is to advance the development of foundation models and self-supervised pre-training methods for brain MRI analysis, with a focus on methodological innovation rather than immediate clinical deployment. While the downstream tasks (infarct classification, meningioma segmentation, and brain age estimation) have potential clinical relevance, this challenge specifically evaluates the ability of foundation models to generalize to these tasks in few-shot learning scenarios, and under domain shifts. Additional work, validation, and regulatory approval would be required before any of these methods could be implemented in clinical practice.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

This challenge is not part of a workshop.

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

Half day

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

The challenge results will be combined with talks from invited speakers on foundation models for medical imaging as well as presentations from top-performing participating teams. The number of teams presenting will be decided based on the total number of participants and the available time.

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

We expect the challenge to attract the interest of a substantial number of submissions for each individual category, with around 30 entries anticipated per task. However, we foresee fewer submissions—approximately 10—that tackle all categories collectively. This limited figure reflects the complexity of pre-training models, despite their growing significance in the field.

We are very focused on lowering the technical bar for participating in this challenge. For this reason we will:

- * Release a public GitHub repo with example code that performs both pretraining and fine-tuning using an MAE-pretext task and a small U-Net backbone (20M parameters).
- * Release pretrained checkpoints for this small, simple baseline model, allowing participants with access to smaller compute environments to investigate continual-pretraining and advanced finetuning techniques.
- * Release code and data that allow users to start pretraining and finetuning with no additional preprocessing.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

The aim is a publication in a journal such as Nature Methods, Medical Image Analysis, npj Digital Medicine, Nature Communications, TMI or NeuroImage. Expected journal submission Q4 2025.

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

Participants are required to train models using their own compute environment. The minimum practical requirement for participation is estimated to be one compute node with at least one GPU with 40 GB of VRAM. On such an environment, with one A100 with 40 GB of VRAM, the baseline model (MAE, U-Net with 20M parameters) takes approximately 48 hours to pre-train and 8-10 hours to fine-tune per task. We expect participants to significantly benefit from larger compute environments. To decrease the participation barrier, we are further

releasing pre-trained checkpoints for a small, simple baseline model, allowing participants with access to smaller compute environments to investigate continual pre-training and advanced fine-tuning techniques.

TASK 1: Infarct Classification

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

The focus of this task is to evaluate the pre-trained models on the task of few-shot image-level infarct classification. Fine-tuning and evaluation datasets consist of real-world, clinical data from two different distributions.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

few-shot classification, robustness, clinical data

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

This challenge is jointly organized by researchers from Pioneer Centre for AI, University of Copenhagen, Massachusetts General Hospital & Harvard Medical School and Bispebjerg & Frederiksberg Hospital, Copenhagen, Copenhagen Research Centre for Biological and Precision Psychiatry & Gentofte Hospital and the Copenhagen-based startup Cerebriu.

Department of Computer Science, University of Copenhagen & Pioneer Centre For AI:

- * Asbjørn Munk, PhD Student
- * Mostafa Mehdipour Ghazi, Assistant Professor
- * Sebastian Llambias, Software Developer
- * Jakob Ambsdorf, PhD Student
- * Julia Machnio, PhD Student
- * Mads Nielsen, Professor

Athinoula A. Martinos Center for Biomedical Imaging, Massachusetts General Hospital & Harvard Medical School:

- * Peirong Liu, Postdoc
- * Juan Eugenio Iglesias, Associate Professor

Radiological AI Testcenter at Bispebjerg and Frederiksberg Hospital:

- * Christian Hedeager Krag, MD, PhD Student, Radiology
- * Trine Balschmidt, MD, PhD Student, Radiology
- * Mikael Boesen, Professor

Copenhagen Research Centre for Biological and Precision Psychiatry & Gentofte Hospital:

* Stefano Cerri, Postdoc

* Vardan Nersesjan, MD, PhD, Neurology

* Michael Eriksen Benros, Professor

Cerebriu A/S

* Akshay Pai, CTO

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Asbjørn Munk, asmu@di.ku.dk

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

This is a one-time event with fixed conference submission deadline. Depending on the outcomes and feedback, we are open to repeating this challenge. The pre-training data will remain available for use after the submission deadline, which we expect to be a significant contribution to the development of foundation models for brain MRI going forward. Further, we are currently exploring technical solutions for keeping the leaderboard open after the challenge has concluded, however this remains a significant technical challenge due to the information security requirements for the compute platform storing the evaluation data.

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

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b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

[Synapse.org](https://synapse.org)

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

The challenge website is accessible through <https://fomo25.github.io>. The Synapse link will be <https://www.synapse.org/Synapse:syn64895667/wiki/630965>, which will be linked to from the main challenge website.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

For all tasks, the challenge will have two tracks: 1. **No additional data allowed:** Challenge participants can only use data provided in the challenge for their submissions. 2. **Any data allowed:** Challenge participants can use any data, including private data, for their submissions. This track includes submissions using any form of segmentation maps obtained through manual labor or disease diagnosis information during pre-training. All data used must be specified and properly cited.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

Due to the large number of members in the institutes of the organizers, these are divided into two groups: 1. Participants who have active working relations with any of the organizers are not allowed to participate and will not be listed on the leaderboard. 2. Other members of the institutes may participate, but are not eligible for awards and listed with a clearly visible disclaimer in leaderboard.

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The challenge will seek to raise funding for prize money in the order of magnitude of \$1000 in total for, but not limited to, the top three teams, defined as the teams with the best ranking on the unified leaderboard in the track using no additional data. We will also seek to raise funding for per-task prizes and for the other track.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

The full leaderboards for the test data will be announced at the conference. The top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly at the conference. Top participants will be invited to present their methods during an oral presentation.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

All participating teams that have made substantial submissions (e.g. excludes trivial approaches such as setting all outputs to zero, random guessing, or simply using provided baselines) to all three tasks will be invited to participate in the following publication. Each team can have at most five authors on the publication, however we will consider exemptions on a case-by-case basis.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Docker container on the Synapse platform. Submission instructions will be available at <https://fomo25.github.io> including example code and example docker container. The submission is subject to a runtime limit of 120 seconds per case on a compute node with an 80GB VRAM H100 GPU and 32 CPUs.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participants will be able to evaluate their algorithms on a held-out validation set before the final submission. The validation dataset will be available for more than one month and participants will be allowed to evaluate their algorithms multiple times.

In the validation period, evaluation will be run once a week until the submission deadline. There is no limit on the number of submissions from participants, but only the most recent model will be evaluated per participant per task per week. This will give participants clear signals on the performance of their models, but discourage over-optimization on the validation split.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

1. April: Challenge registration opens, including access to pre-training dataset and fine-tuning data. Release public GitHub repo with example code that performs both pre-training and fine-tuning using an MAE-pretext task and a small U-Net backbone (20M parameters).

15. April. Access to sanity-check pipeline on Synapse opens (technical evaluation which confirms that Docker image is correctly configured).

15. June: Validation leaderboard opens and final submission pipeline opens.

20. August: Challenge submission deadline.

Results will be released during MICCAI 2025 (22 September or 28 September).

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

All datasets have been approved by legal and ethics boards, including the Danish Patient Safety (Styrelsen for Patientsikkerhed, approval #31-1521-257) and the Danish Data Protection Agency (Datatilsynet, approval #P-2020-320). The pre-training source dataset denoted as "MGH Wild" was downloaded from the PACS at Massachusetts General Hospital under Institutional Review Board approval.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Pre-training data may be used for any purpose that aligns with the usage terms of the individual source datasets. These terms will be clearly outlined on the challenge website, and participants must explicitly agree to them through the data access process. Fine-tuning data is restricted exclusively to use within the scope of this challenge and cannot be used for any purpose beyond submitting entries for the competition. Validation and test data will remain private and accordingly are not subject to any usage policies.

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

All evaluation code will be made public. Code is based on the Yucca framework [1], which is publicly available on Pypi and closely mimics the way nnUnet [2] performs evaluation. The evaluation script can be used on any machine which supports PyTorch >2.0.0.

[1] Llambias, S.N., Machnio, J., Munk, A., Ambsdorf, J., Nielsen, M., Ghazi, M.M.: Yucca: A deep learning framework for medical image analysis. arXiv preprint arXiv:2407.19888 (2024), <https://arxiv.org/abs/2407.19888>

[2] Isensee, F., Jaeger, P.F., Kohl, S.A.A., Petersen, J., Maier-Hein, K.: nnu-net: a self-configuring method for deep learning-based biomedical image segmentation. Nature Methods 18, 203 – 211 (2020), <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41592-020-01008-z>

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Submissions and code of participating teams will not be made public, participants are free to publicize their submissions at their own discretion.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Mads Nielsen owns shares of Cerebriu, who is co-organizer of this challenge.

Only Stefano Cerri, Sebastian Llambias, Asbjørn Munk, Vardan Nersesjan and Christian Hedager Krag have had access to the test labels. The access to this have been in the following three contexts:

- * Producing the labels.
- * Writing evaluation code.
- * Executing evaluation of submissions.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling

- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Few-shot Classification

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

18-year-old or older patients with possible brain infarct(s).

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Subjects who underwent an MRI scan and was subsequently diagnosed with infarcts and a control group in 2019 in multiple hospitals in Denmark (evaluation data) and India (fine-tuning data).

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

MRI scans of the brain, always including T2 FLAIR, DWI (b-value 1000), and either T2* or SWI images, are used for the Fine-tuning, Validation, and Test datasets.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Pre-train: None. Fine-tune: binary mask of infarct. Validation and Testing: None

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Pre-train: None. Fine-tune: age and patient sex. Validation and Testing: None

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Brain MRI scans.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Image-based classification of patients with brain infarcts, scanned with clinically routine MRI.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Binary classification of the presence or absence of infarcts on MRI scans. AUROC, Robustness, Few-shot Generalisation

DATA SETS**Data source(s)**

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Pre-train dataset: multiple scanners from different vendors. Fine-tune dataset: multiple scanners from GE and Siemens. Validation and Test datasets: multiple scanners from GE, Siemens, and Philips.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The acquisition protocols are highly heterogeneous and vary across hospitals, as scans were acquired during real-world routine clinical practice. Detailed information about the acquisition parameters for each scan will be made available as supplementary material in the challenge meta-analysis manuscript.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Pre-train: highly diverse dataset from the following public sources: OASIS3 [1], OASIS4 [2], PPMI [3], BraTS21 [4], ISLES22 [5], MSD Braintumor [6], IXI [7], SOOP [8], and MGH Wild [9]. For the MICCAI challenge datasets where splits are available, only the training-split of the datasets has been used.

Fine-tune dataset: Bodyscan Diagnostics, Indore, India. The dataset contains data from multiple hospitals related to Bodyscan Diagnostics and has been provided by the Copenhagen-based startup Cerebriu. Validation and test datasets: Rigshospitalet, Copenhagen; Bispebjerg & Frederiksberg Hospital, Copenhagen; Nordsjællands Hospital, Hillerød; Bornholms Hospital, Rønne; Amager & Hvidovre Hospital, Copenhagen; Herlev & Gentofte Hospital,

Copenhagen. All hospitals are located in The Capital Region of Denmark. The datasets of fine-tuning and validation are taken from different source distributions in order to gauge the generalization abilities of the pre-trained models under domain shift, while harmonizing the MRI sequence types and labeling protocols.

[1] LaMontagne, P., Benzinger, T., Morris, J., Keefe, S., Hornbeck, R., Xiong, C., Grant, E., Hassenstab, J., Moulder, K., Vlassenko, A., Raichle, M., Cruchaga, C., Marcus, D.: Oasis-3: Longitudinal neuroimaging, clinical, and cognitive dataset for normal aging and alzheimer disease (12 2019). <https://doi.org/10.1101/2019.12.13.19014902>

[2] Select Atrophied Regions in Alzheimer disease (SARA): An improved volumetric model for identifying Alzheimer disease dementia. Koenig, L et al 2020. *NeuroImage Clinical*, 26,102248. doi: 10.1016/j.nicl.2020.102248

[3] Marek, K., et. al.: The parkinson progression marker tive (PPMI). *Progress in Neurobiology*, Volume 95, Issue 4, 2011, Pages 629-635, ISSN 0301-0082, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pneurobio.2011.09.005>.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0301008211001651>.

[4] Guzman Perez-Carrillo, G et. al.: The RSNA-ASNR-MICCAI BraTS 2021 benchmark on brain tumor segmentation and radiogenomic classification (09 2021)

[5] 20. Petzsche, M., de la Rosa, E., Hanning, U., Wiest, R., Valenzuela, W., Reyes, M., Meyer, M., Liew, S.L., Kofler, F., Ezhov, I., Robben, D., Hutton, A., Friedrich, T., Zarth, T., Bu rkle, J., Baran, T., Menze, B., Broocks, G., Meyer, L., Kirschke, J.: Isles 2022: A multi-center magnetic resonance imaging stroke lesion segmentation dataset. *Scientific Data* 9, 762 (12 2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01875-5>

[6] Simpson, A., Antonelli, M., Bakas, S., Bilello, M., Farahani, K., Ginneken, B., Kopp-Schneider, A., Landman, B., Litjens, G., Menze, B., Ronneberger, O., Summers, R., Bilic, P., Christ, P., Do, R., Gollub, M., Golia-Pernicka, J., Heckers, S., Jarnagin, W., Cardoso, M.J.: A large annotated medical image dataset for the development and evaluation of segmentation algorithms (02 2019).

[7] <http://brain-development.org/ixi-dataset/>

[8] Chris Rorden and John Absher and Roger Newman-Norlund (2024). Stroke Outcome Optimization Project (SOOP). OpenNeuro. [Dataset] doi: doi:10.18112/openneuro.ds004889.v1.1.2

[9] Juan E. Iglesias et al. ,SynthSR: A public AI tool to turn heterogeneous clinical brain scans into high-resolution T1-weighted images for 3D morphometry. *Sci. Adv.* 9, eadd3607(2023). DOI:10.1126/sciadv.add3607.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Healthcare professionals responsible for performing MRI scans on patients with possible brain-related conditions during regular clinical workflows.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific MRI visit. For Fine-tuning, Validation and Test datasets, information always includes T2-FLAIR and DWI (b-value 1000), and either T2* or SWI MRI scans, image-level label indicating the presence or absence of infarct(s), and patient demographic (age and sex). Each fine-tuning case belonging to the positive class has an additional binary segmentation mask delineating the infarct.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Pre-training cases: 11161. Fine-tune cases: 24. Validation cases: 80. Test cases: 320.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

- * Pre-training dataset is the largest publicly available pre-training dataset for brain MRI.
- * The fine-tuning dataset is kept small to condition the performance on the quality of the pre-training and to evaluate the model's few-shot performance under domain shifts.
- * The validation dataset is kept small to only gauge the performance of the methods under distribution shift.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

13 fine-tuning cases are from the positive class (presence of infarcts) and 11 are from the negative class (absence of infarcts). The validation and test cases have equal class distribution.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

Fine-tuning, Validation, and Test datasets are all completely unseen.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Pre-training dataset: None. Fine-tuning, Validation, and Test datasets: Positive examples were selected based on ICD-10 codes D32.0 and C70.0. Image-level annotation of the presence or absence of infarcts was then confirmed by one expert annotator. We are working on getting a second annotator to confirm a subset in order to estimate

intra-rater agreement. Negative examples were selected based on the absence of ICD-10 codes D32.0 and C70.0 and radiology reports were scanned to confirm no potential presence of infarcts.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Image-level classification of infarcts (presence (positive class) or absence (negative class)) was performed primarily using T2-FLAIR scans. In cases where potential infarct areas on FLAIR were unclear, DWI, T2* and/or SWI scans were utilized to confirm or rule out the presence of acute or subacute infarcts.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Two expert annotators were used with expertise in Radiology and Neurology, respectively. Both annotators are medical doctors, and have completed at least the 1st year of residency in their respective fields. One annotator has obtained a PhD in Neurology, and another annotator is in their final year of a PhD in Radiology.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Disagreements among raters will be assessed and finalised by a third rater.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

All datasets will be minimally processed to allow users to define and control data processing pipelines. Each individual scan is RAS-oriented using Yucca, skull-stripped using SynthSeg, and each sequence is affinely coregistered using mri_coreg to the highest resolution scan in the same MRI visit, or, when manual delineations are available, to the reference scan used for delineation. For scans in the pre-training dataset, only processing steps not already performed by their respective organizers were applied.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter- and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Labels for the Validation and Test datasets are derived from ICD-10 codes (D32.0 and C70.0) and created manually, introducing potential subjectivity and error.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Multi-class counting metrics: N/A

Per-class counting metric: N/A

Multi-threshold metrics: AUROC (Area Under the Receiver Operator Curve (ROC))

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The metrics have been chosen by following the recommendations set forth in Metrics Reloaded [1]. The following contains the problem-specific answers for Image-level classification:

Question: Which cutoff method on predicted class scores fits your problem more?

Answer: No decision rule applied

Justification: This challenge seeks to make methodological comparisons, with no concrete clinical use-case in mind.

Question: Are predicted class probabilities available in your research?

Answer: Yes

Question: Do the provided class prevalences reflect the population of interest in your research?

Answer: No

Question: Is calibration assessment requested in your research?

Answer: No

We follow the recommendation of not including any per-class counting metrics and to evaluate models using AUROC.

[1] Maier-Hein et al. Metrics reloaded: recommendations for image analysis validation. Nature methods, 21(2):195–212, 2024.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

For each task, all test cases are assigned uniform weight and each metric is averaged over all cases in the test set.

The ranking procedure will follow those used in previous challenges like TIGER and DECATHLON.

Per-task leaderboard:

A summary statistic defined as the average of all metrics in the task is used to make a per-task rank.

Unified leaderboard:

For each pretraining configuration, the same pretrained checkpoint can be fine-tuned to each of the three tasks. Per pre-training checkpoint, an overall rank is then calculated as the average rank of each task. For partial submissions, that is submissions that have only submitted models for a subset of the three tasks, the worst possible rank is used in the average (defined as number of valid submissions per task plus one.)

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

For missing metric values for test cases, submissions are evaluated by setting the score to the worst possible value. For AUROC the worst possible value is 0.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

A leaderboard provides a concise summary of results, offering a clear comparison across tasks, and is both simple to implement and to interpret.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

The ranks will be complemented with statistical analysis focusing on the significance of model performance. The significance of each model will be assessed by permuting the relative ranks of each metric and task on a subject-by-subject basis within the test set. Pairwise p-values will be calculated to assess the statistical significance of differences between the ranked approaches. These p-values will be presented in an upper triangular matrix, highlighting statistically insignificant differences among teams, which will be grouped into tiers. This methodology ensures a thorough and reliable evaluation of performance and ranking consistency, and is based on the methodology developed by the BraTS challenge series and [1].

[1] S. Bakas et al., Identifying the Best Machine Learning Algorithms for Brain Tumor Segmentation, Progression Assessment, and Overall Survival Prediction in the BRATS Challenge, arXiv:1811.02629 [cs, stat], Apr. 2019, Accessed: Dec. 10, 2020. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1811.02629>.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

Permutation testing is performed in order to highlight performance difference greater than those which could reasonably be expected by chance.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,

- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

Further analyses will seek to investigate the correlation between performance and:

- * Different pretraining methodologies, grouping by similar methodological categories (e.g. reconstruction vs. self-distillation vs. contrastive learning etc)
- * Using private data, specifically on the impact of pretraining dataset size.
- * Different backbones.
- * Model sizes and capacities, measured in FLOPS and total number of parameters.

The analysis is not limited to the above, and may include the relationship between performance and other attributes of the submissions.

TASK 2: Meningioma Segmentation

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

The focus of this task is to evaluate the pre-trained models on the task of few-shot segmentation. Fine-tuning and evaluation datasets consist of real-world, clinical data from two different distributions.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

few-shot segmentation, robustness, clinical data

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

See task 1.

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Asbjørn Munk, asmu@di.ku.dk

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

See task 1.

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

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b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

See task 1.

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

See task 1.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

See task 1.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

See task 1.

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

See task 1.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

See task 1.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

See task 1.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

See task 1.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to

compute challenge results.

See task 1.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

See task 1.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

See task 1.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

See task 1.

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

See task 1.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

See task 1.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

See task 1.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval

- Segmentation
- Tracking

Few-shot Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

18-year-old or older preoperative meningioma patients.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Subjects who underwent an MRI diagnosed with preoperative meningioma in 2019 in multiple hospitals in Denmark (evaluation data) and India (fine-tuning data).

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

MRI scans of the brain, always including T2 FLAIR, DWI (b-value 1000), and either T2* or SWI images, are used for the Fine-tuning, Validation, and Test datasets.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Pre-train: None. Fine-tune: binary mask of meningiomas. Validation and Testing: None

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Pre-train: None. Fine-tune: age and patient sex. Validation and Testing: None

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Brain MRI scans.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Patients with brain meningiomas scanned with clinically routine MRI.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Binary segmentation of brain meningiomas on MRI scans. Dice, Normalized Surface Distance, Robustness, Few-shot Generalisation

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Pre-train dataset: same as Task 1. Fine-tune dataset: multiple scanners from GE, Siemens, and Philips. Validation and Test datasets: multiple scanners from GE, Siemens, and Philips.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

See task 1.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

See task 1.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Healthcare professionals responsible for performing MRI scans on patients with possible brain-related conditions during regular clinical workflows.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).

- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific MRI visit. For Fine-tuning, Validation and Test datasets, information always includes T2-FLAIR and DWI (b-value 1000), and either T2* or SWI MRI scans, patient demographics (age and sex), and a binary segmentation mask delineating the meningiomas.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Pre-training cases: same as Task 1. Fine-tune cases: 22. Validation cases: 40. Test cases: 160.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

See task 1.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

Not applicable.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

Fine-tuning, Validation, and Test datasets are all completely unseen.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Manual image annotation of the meningiomas. For fine-tuning, validation, and test cases, the delineation has been performed by one annotator. We are currently working on annotating a subset of the dataset with a second annotator in order to estimate intra-rater agreement.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The manual delineation protocol follows the BraTS Meningioma Segmentation Challenge [1], with the only difference being that we provide binary masks instead of multi-label masks.

[1] LaBella et al., "A multi-institutional meningioma MRI dataset for automated multi-sequence image segmentation," Scientific Data, 11:496, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-024-03350-9>.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

See task 1.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Multiple annotations will be merged using the STAPLE [1] algorithm.

[1] Warfield SK, Zou KH, Wells WM. Simultaneous truth and performance level estimation (STAPLE): an algorithm for the validation of image segmentation. IEEE Trans Med Imaging. 2004 Jul;23(7):903-21. doi: 10.1109/TMI.2004.828354. PMID: 15250643; PMCID: PMC1283110.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

See task 1.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Manual delineations by expert annotators may contain errors due to subjective bias. Delineations from a different annotator on a subset of the dataset for overlapping cases will be released before the challenge, and intra-annotator variability will be assessed.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Overlap-based metric: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)

Boundary-based metric: Normal Surface Distance (NSD)

Volume metric: N/A

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The metrics have been chosen by following the recommendations set forth in Metrics Reloaded [1]. The following contains the problem-specific answers for semantic segmentation:

Question: Does your data feature consistently small structures relative to pixel size?

Answer: No

Question: Is there exclusive interest in structure centers in your research?

Answer: No

Question: According to the this information, do class confusions, i.e., over- vs. undersegmentation, have equal or unequal weight in your study?

Answer: Equal handling

Question: Are there overlapping or touching target structures in your data?

Answer: No

Question: Is there particular importance of structure boundaries in your research?

Answer: Yes

Question: Is compensation for annotation imprecisions requested in your research?

Answer: Yes

We follow the recommendation of using the following metrics:

Overlap-based metric: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)

Boundary-based metric: Normal Surface Distance (NSD)

We have decided to not use any volume metric since this challenge seeks to make methodological comparisons, with no concrete clinical use-case in mind.

[1] Maier-Hein et al. Metrics reloaded: recommendations for image analysis validation. Nature methods, 21(2):195–212, 2024.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

See task 1.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

For missing metric values for test cases, submissions are evaluated by setting the score to the worst possible value. For DSC and NSD the worst possible value is 0.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

See task 1.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

See task 1.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

See task 1.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

See task 1.

TASK 3: Brain Age Estimation

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

The focus of this task is to evaluate the pre-trained models on the task of regression. Fine-tuning and evaluation datasets consist of real-world, clinical data from two different distributions.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

regression, robustness, clinical data

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

See task 1.

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Asbjørn Munk, asmu@di.ku.dk

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

See task 1.

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

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b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

See task 1.

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

See task 1.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

See task 1.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

See task 1.

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

See task 1.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

See task 1.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

See task 1.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

See task 1.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to

compute challenge results.

See task 1.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

See task 1.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

See task 1. The fine-tuning dataset was downloaded from the PACS at Massachusetts General Hospital under Institutional Review Board approval.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

See task 1.

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

See task 1.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

See task 1.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

See task 1.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration

- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Regression

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Patients 18 years or older with no underlying brain conditions defined as patients with no neurological conditions and not on brain-related medication.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Subjects who underwent an MRI with no underlying brain conditions in 2019 in multiple hospitals in Denmark (evaluation data) and Boston (fine-tuning data).

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

MRI scans of the brain, always including T1w and T2w images for Fine-tuning, Validation and Test datasets.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Pre-train, Fine-tune, Validation and Testing: None

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Pre-train: None. Fine-tune: age and patient sex. Validation and Testing: None

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Brain MRI scans.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Age of patients with no underlying brain conditions, scanned with clinically routine MRI.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accurate prediction of the age of the patient based on MRI scans. ,Robustness

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Pre-train dataset: same as Task 1. Fine-tune dataset: multiple scanners from GE, Siemens, and Philips. Validation and Test datasets: multiple scanners from GE, Siemens, and Philips.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

See task 1.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Fine-tune dataset: Massachusetts General Hospital, a subset from MGH Wild [1]. For other datasets, see Task 1.

[1] Juan E. Iglesias et al. ,SynthSR: A public AI tool to turn heterogeneous clinical brain scans into high-resolution T1-weighted images for 3D morphometry.Sci. Adv.9,eadd3607(2023).DOI:10.1126/sciadv.add3607.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Healthcare professionals responsible for performing MRI scans on patients with possible brain-related conditions during regular clinical workflows.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific MRI visit. For Fine-Tuning, Validation and Test datasets, information always includes T1w and T2w MRI scans, and patient demographics (age and sex).

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Pre-training cases: same as Task 1. Fine-tune cases: 100. Validation Cases: 200. Test cases: 800

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

See task 1.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

Not applicable.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

Validation, and Test datasets are all completely unseen.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

For each case, age at the time of the MRI visit is provided.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Not applicable

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Not applicable

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

No multiple annotations are available.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

See task 1.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Although we exclude patients with neurological conditions and those on brain-related medication, non-brain conditions may still indirectly affect brain age estimation, introducing potential errors and biases.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Metric 1: Absolute Error (AE)

Metric 2: Correlation Coefficient

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

Since Metrics Reloaded [1] does not incorporate regression recommendations, we cannot follow the same structured approach as in Task 1 and Task 2.

Using AE and the correlation coefficient provides a complementary evaluation: AE measures prediction accuracy while being intuitive and interpretable, while the correlation coefficient assesses the alignment of predictions while penalizing systematic biases.

[1] Maier-Hein et al. Metrics reloaded: recommendations for image analysis validation. Nature methods, 21(2):195–212, 2024.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

See task 1. The summary statistic is the average of the per-metric ranks.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

For the Absolute Error: Submissions are evaluated by setting the absolute error to the worst possible value for the test, defined as the value 100.

For correlation coefficient: missing test case predictions are set to -100, and this value is used to calculate the correlation coefficient.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

See task 1.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

See task 1.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

See task 1.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

See task 1.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

References are given in each field.

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A